

ADJUSTING THE MASSIVELY OPEN ONLINE COURSES IN CLOUD COMPUTING ENVIRONMENT⁹

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Abstract

Massively Open Online Courses (MOOC) is new trending model for delivering learning content online to any person with no limit on attendance for everyone that wishes to attend to a course. Following the MOOC trend there is an expectation that till 2015 there will be more than 6 million unique students worldwide. In order to provide appropriate quality learning user experience for the students we propose how to optimize the cloud computing resources, such as Virtual Machine (VM) distribution per contents to support the MOOC. For this purpose we have used a simulation tool, called CloudAnalyst, which supports visual modelling and simulation of large-scale applications that are deployed on cloud infrastructures. The results will provide information for the geographic distribution of traffic and location of data centres and number of resources for each data centre.

Key words: Massively Open Online Courses, Coursera, Cloud Computing, CloudAnalyst.

INTRODUCTION

University study provides students with the opportunity to learn by working in groups during class time, presenting their work in class, and even collaborating together on a project, which as we all know is happening in real-time. Recently, there is a need to shift from a monolithic *learning environment* in which everything must be controlled and predictable to a more pluralistic *learning ecology* in which both prescriptive and emergent IT application domains and models of learning have their place [1]. Another research, had asked participants in *online learning environment* to describe their learning experience in the context of multiple communities and found that there's an apparent importance of expressing new perspectives across

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multiple communities that spring from online courses [2]. Using this approach, students are expanding the ability for creating, sharing and collaborating through emerging technologies such as blogs, wikis, podcasts, and social networks. In the same time professors and teaching assistants will spent less time on lecturing the students, and they can be more effective in scaffolding and tutoring the students to improve their skills.

Recent research has proposed cloud computing (CC) to be used as approach for online user-assessment and classification of learning materials, in order to provide personalized resource recommendation [3]. The last two years there is a trend called massively open online course (MOOC), which have generated wide attention due to initiatives made by high-profile institutions such as Stanford and MIT, which have formed start-ups such as Coursera, Udacity, and edX [4]. Distance learning and the MOOC have a great potential for informal and lifelong learning. The MOOC presents important challenge related to student engagement and evaluation, in order to ensure an exceptional student experience and to avoid high dropout rates researchers are using pedagogic approach by experiential learning and collaborative learning theories [4]. The MOOC allows hosting university to open its curriculum to a wider audience. In order to be able to support simultaneously large number of users from all around the world there needs to be optimal distribution of CC resources. Considering that nowadays the trend of MOOC reputation is to be able to deliver real-time uninterrupted delivery of multimedia contents promptly to all students [5]. The main contribution in this paper is to provide appropriate optimal configuration of CC environment for the providers of MOOC to deliver high-quality learning material. To be able to provide finest configuration of CC environment we have used simulation tool, called CloudAnalyst, to plan the resources needed for MOOC to be accessible and reliable worldwide.

This paper is organized as follows: Firstly we present the concept of the cloud-based massively open online courses. Next it is described the simulation of MOOC use case and comparison of two simulations with CloudAnalyst. At the end is provided discussion for the results and conclusion of the paper.

CLOUD-BASED MASSIVELY OPEN ONLINE COURSES

The MOOC networks can be used for creating, sharing, and refining the knowledge between the participants. Learners are encouraged to represent their knowledge or questions through diversity of platforms and to connect to each other around issues and topics of shared interest. That way,

MOOC builds a model of collaborative networks of unprecedented rapidly expanding educational resources. The MOOC environment is a self-guided course that could have thousands of participants. It requires that a participant is willing to engage, and has some confidence and comfort with the discourses of an autodidact and a self-starter [5]. MOOC offers opportunities for interaction of student with the material as well as student with their peers. The open online course can be used by potentially large number of students from all over the world. The real potential of MOOC is that CC based support for the emergence of learning networks among participants in a many-to-many relationship, rather than the traditional one-to-many model of interactions between a teacher and his or her students [6].

Common for all MOOC providers is that all of them have been established during 2012 by leading world universities and they all have large number of participants. Another common feature for MOOCs is that they are cloud-based learning platforms. The Google Engine platform is the base for Udacity and Khan Academy, whereas, the Amazon Web Service Infrastructure is support for Coursera, Instructure, LoudCloud Systems and Lore [7]. Considering the significant large number of students enrolled in Coursera we have decided to conduct further and deeper research for this MOOC. The popularity of Coursera in world scale, broken down by country [8], is given in Figure 1 (left). Another research made by Outsell [9] have estimated that by the end of 2012, about 3.17 million unique students worldwide were enrolled in courses from the major MOOC providers, see Figure 1 (right). Following the MOOC trend and popularity they are expecting that till 2015 there will be more than 3 million unique students only from North and South America, and the rest of 3 million unique students will be from other worldwide continents [9].

MOOCs allow learning to happen across space and time due to its mainly asynchronous and online architecture. The MOOC is a gathering of people with generally good internet connection, it has a unique social advantage that relates to a more open and connected way of thinking. Considering that nowadays the trend of MOOC reputation the providers should be able to deliver real-time uninterrupted delivery of multimedia contents promptly to all students. In order to provide appropriate and optimal configuration of CC environment for the MOOC providers we will use the CloudAnalyst simulator.

Figure 1. Country distribution [8] (left), Global MOOC audience [9] (right)

In this research we have used CloudAnalyst [10] to model a simulated environment to study the behavior of a MOOC platform in CC environment. It provides graphical output in the form of tables and charts is highly desirable to summarize the potentially large amount of statistics that is collected during the simulation. The simulator is developed on Java platform, using Java SE 1.6, and the GUI component is built using Swing components [10]. CloudAnalyst, built on top of CloudSim, allows description of application workloads, including information of geographic location of users generating traffic and location of data centers, number of users and data centers, and number of resources in each data center [10]. A User Base models a group of users that is considered as a single unit in the simulation and its main responsibility is to generate traffic for the simulation. We have used Throttled Load Balancer [10] that ensures only a pre-defined number of Internet Cloudlets are allocated to a single VM at any given time. With this balancer if more request groups are present than the number of available VM's at a data center, some of the requests will have to be queued until the next VM becomes available. Modeling bandwidth for a complex network like the MOOC is an extremely difficult task. In the current version of CloudAnalyst it is used a hypothetical parameter, available bandwidth, which is assumed to be the quota of Internet bandwidth available for the application being simulated, ignoring other external factors [10]. For that purpose we model the behavior of MOOC platform for the use case Coursera and using CloudAnalyst we will evaluate time response of data centers and performances related to use of CC to host MOOCs courses worldwide.

A CASE STUDY: SIMULATION OF A MOOC IN CLOUDANALYST

Streaming video requires reasonable quality of bandwidth, and a reasonably new computer with good quality video/graphics card. Most of the MOOC participants from North America in rural and remote communities may face bandwidth challenges similar to their African peers, but even when they do not, challenges still arise with respect to such things as the possession and use of microphones, web cams, and headsets [5]. Also, time zones can also be concerns in MOOCs, especially if regular live sessions are planned. Therefore, the use of synchronous tools should be carefully planned in a MOOC, in order to overcome the issue with different time zones [6]. The CloudAnalyst allows clear overview of analysis for different time zone intervals in different regions of the World. The massive size of the participating group maximizes the possibility for participants to find peers who share complementary interests and skills, and with whom they can collaborate to achieve mutually defined goals. The CloudAnalyst simulator environment, identified by CloudAnalyst Region IDs, is divided into 6 ‘Regions’ that correspond with the 6 main continents in the World. Considering the Coursera students distribution by country, given in Figure 1, we have created the approximate percentage distribution of the Coursera user base across the world is given in Table 1. We have defined 6 user bases representing the above 6 regions corresponding to the CloudAnalyst Region IDs with the following parameters are also given in Table 1.

TABLE I. PERCENTAGE DISTRIBUTION AND USER BASES

User base	Region ID and continent	Users in %	Peak Hours (GMT)	Simultaneous Online Users During Peak Hrs	Simultaneous Online Users During Off-peak Hrs
UB1	0- North America	43,8	02:00-09:00	430,000	43,000
UB2	1- South America	8,9	06:00-13:00	89,000	8,900
UB3	2- Europe	32,9	10:00-17:00	329,000	32,900
UB4	3- Asia	11,9	15:00-22:00	119,000	11,900
UB5	4- Africa	0,9	11:00-18:00	9,000	900
UB6	5- Australia & Oceania	1,6	20:00-03:00	16,000	1,600

For the sake of simplicity in the simulation configuration each user base is contained within a single time zone and it is assumed that most users use the MOOC platform for about 7 hours, per day. Also, it is also assumed that only (1/10) one tenth of that number of users is on line during the off-

peak hours. The cost for hosting Coursera platform in a Cloud is closely following this pricing plan: Cost per VM per hour \$0.10; Cost per 1GB of data transfer (from/to Internet): \$0.10 [17]. Size of virtual machines (VM) in data centers used to host Coursera in the experiment is 10,000MB. The virtual machines have 1GB of RAM memory and have 1000MB of available bandwidth. Simulated hosts have x86 architecture, virtual machine monitor Xen and Linux operating system. Data center nodes have six core L5640 CPU processors 24GB of RAM and 60x600GB Dual channel SAS disks of storage. Each machine has 2 CPUs, and each CPU has a capacity power of 37006 MIPS. A time-shared policy is used to schedule resources to VMs. Users are grouped by a factor of 1000, and requests are grouped by a factor of 100. Each user request requires 4096 instructions to be executed.

a) Scenario 1 – Coursera hosted on a single data center

Considering the centralized approach for Coursera we assume initially the platform is deployed in a single location, in Region 0 (North America). The simulated data center hosts 50 virtual machines dedicated to Coursera, each one with 1024MB of memory in each VM running on physical processors capable of speeds of 37006 MIPS. After running the simulation in CloudAnalyst for the first scenario with single data center we have received the following simulation output, see Table 2. The response times experienced by each user base for the first scenario are shown graphically in Figure 2.

TABLE II. SCENARIO 1: OVERALL RESPONSE AND PROCESSING TIME

	Avg (ms)	Min (ms)	Max (ms)
Overall response time:	1021	91	3018
Data center processing time:	74	0.15	522

Figure 2. Scenario 1: Response time across regions with the single data center

The spikes in response times can be seen clearly during the seven hour peak period, and it can be observed how the peak loads of one user base could affect other user bases as well. The UB1 has the peak between 02:00-09:00 GMT, similar UB3 has significantly increased peak time between 10:00-17:00 GMT and all other user bases have small spikes during this same period. Overall, during the 1 day simulation we can see different distribution depending of the user base region and different peak hours per regions. During the high load of the UB1 peak from Region 0 (North America) the time for processing has been highest compared to the processing times of the other regions.

b) Scenario 2 – Coursera hosted on a two data centers

When Coursera grow in popularity on the Internet the most common approach to improve service quality is to deploy the application in several locations around the globe. Consequently for the second scenario in CloudAnalyst, we kept the user bases the same and we add one more data center, in region 2 (Europe). In order to preserve the cost the same 50 virtual machines are splitted on half for each data center. After running the simulation from second scenario with two data centers we have received the following response time and request processing time, see Table 3.

TABLE III. SCENARIO 2: OVERALL RESPONSE AND PROCESSING TIME

	Avg (ms)	Min (ms)	Max (ms)
Overall response time:	825	75	2535
Data center processing time:	414	0.19	1618

Overall, response time in second scenario is significantly lower than the corresponding response time in first scenario with single data center. Contrary, we have increased data center processing time in the second scenario with two data centers, this is because we are using half of the number of VMs in each data center compared to the first scenario. Substantial improvement in the second scenario is evident for the response time by region where the average response time has balanced distribution, see the second column Avg (ms) from Table 4.

TABLE IV. SCENARIO 2: RESPONSE TIME BY REGION

User Base	Avg (ms)	Min (ms)	Max (ms)
UB1	994,941	92,687	2.535,985
UB2	545,046	189,154	1.738,521
UB3	719,439	75,094	1.817,187
UB4	749,981	280,650	1.335,600
UB5	346,825	259,448	876,667
UB6	208,679	166,418	370,501

Significant difference is noticeable in the data center processing times and response times shown in Figure 3. The average processing time of both data centers is increased because of the decreased number of VMs. In the same time we can notice decreased loading traffic for the first data center (DC1), now the peak is 6M requests per hour. Reducing the number of virtual machines by half during each of these peak loads effectively lengthens the time taken to process by about two times in each data center.

Figure 3. Scenario 2: Data center processing and loading times

Considering the MOOC trend there is an expectation that till 2015 there will be more than 6 million unique students worldwide. In this research we were able to conduct excellent analysis using the simulator CloudAnalyst and we received substantial improvement for the response time in the 6 regions and lowered loading traffic for the first data center (DC1).

CONCLUSION

We have researched the massive online teaching infrastructures on a worldwide scale because it offers remarkable collaborative and conversational opportunities for students to gather and discuss the course content. We demonstrated how CloudAnalyst can be used to model and evaluate a real world MOOC through a case study of a Coursera deployed on the cloud. We have illustrated how the simulator can be used to effectively identify overall usage patterns and how such usage patterns affect data centers hosting the application. This paper provides appropriate configuration for distribution of the resources by geographic location depending on the workload of CC environment for the providers of MOOC to deliver high-quality learning material. We have proposed to use environment with two data centers, one in North America and the other in Europe, in order to bringing the service closer to the users. This improves the response time in the 6 regions and has shown how to improve the Coursera load balancing at the application level across data centers.

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